

Sekmokas, M., Sai, A., Friedel, M. & Tilon, N. (2023). Modelling skills mismatch evolution in the European Union. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 407–423). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7822461>

Modelling Skills Mismatch Evolution in the European Union

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Abstract

Ensuring, that the supply of skills matches their demand in the labour market is a persistent policy concern. As a consequence, there are regular efforts to estimate skills supply-demand imbalances and project their evolution over time. However, such projections may not always take into account the complex dynamic effects, present in education and labour market systems. System dynamics (SD) modelling is well-placed to take into account such effects. Therefore, this paper attempts to model the evolution of supply, demand and imbalances of skills in the European Union, also taking into account dynamic factors, such as policy choices (e.g., education financing) and/or socio-economic tendencies (e.g., the attractiveness of higher education). The modelling exercise demonstrates that SD may be used to model skills supply-demand systems and that it can be calibrated to perform in line with historical data. Using this model, the future projection of skills mismatch evolution indicates, that by the mid-2030s an over-supply of high-skilled labour may appear in the EU. This may also happen much earlier if post-secondary VET qualifications would be considered well-matched with some of the jobs requiring a high level of skills, as has been argued to be the case by some authors earlier. There is a potential for further refining and extending this analysis with a more detailed definition of mismatch, longer time series, country-level data analysis and broadening geographical coverage.

Keywords

skills mismatches, education, labour market, system dynamics

1 Introduction

There is a persistent policy concern as to what extent the available workforce skills correspond to the skills requirements of jobs and how well the education systems can close any such gaps. The pan-European policy objectives of improving the skills of European citizens via the EU

skills policy testify to this concern (European Commission, 2020). In response to this policy challenge, there have been a number of efforts to estimate skills supply, demand and the imbalances between the two, as well as develop projections of their evolution into the future (Biagi et al., 2020; Sekmokas et al., 2020; CEDEFOP, 2018).

System dynamics (SD) is a useful tool to provide insights into the evolution of complex systems as well as provide decision support. In particular, it can help reveal complex, non-linear behaviour, thus enhancing understanding and anticipation of changes. Multiple examples exist in applying SD for strategic workforce planning, for example at a firm (Größler and Zock, 2010) or a sectoral (Willis and Kunc, 2018) level. The aim of this paper is to develop an SD model covering the whole labour market of a large territorial entity – the European Union.

2 A concise review of the literature

Multiple domains in the social sciences and humanities are pursuing questions related to education and work - with sociology and economics, in particular, having a large corpus of research available. In economics, for example, human capital theory is a dominant perspective on how individuals and households make decisions to invest in education and how these generate returns in the labour market (Kremer and Holla, 20019). Sociology, conversely, is often focused on exploring the causes and consequences of inequalities and social stratification - both within education as well as work, going beyond purely economic perspective (Buchmann and Hannum, 2001).

When studying the phenomena of mismatches between education and work, insights from the human capital theory can often be informative. This theory is based on the assumption, that more (less) education than required for a particular profession leads to a return (or penalty), for example, in wages, which would compensate the initial investment in schooling (Bauer, 2002). However, there have been attempts to counterweight this theory with alternative perspectives.

For example, the human capital compensation hypothesis, which is based on the notion that over-educated persons compensate for a lack of other human capital qualities by attaining more schooling than required for a given job, whereas under-qualified workers show strengths in other human capital areas, compensating the lacking years of education (Rubb, 2006; Korpi & Tåhlin, 2006). Thus, it may not be appropriate to measure and explain the extent of mismatch solely on the basis of scholarly education. In summary, according to the compensation theory, the observed educational mismatches do not reflect actual mismatches but rather individual heterogeneity across the working individuals (Korpi & Tåhlin, 2006).

Another alternative theory is the so-called "signaling theory". It suggests that the effect of education may be realized not by changing individuals (i.e., by enhancing their skills), but as a communication tool. Given that it is difficult to observe the actual capabilities of job applicants, education can be an instrument for individuals to showcase to potential employers that they have stronger innate skills and/or attitudes as compared to their peers, who were not able/willing to achieve the same level of education (Ghazarian, 2015).

A further angle to investigate the correlation between higher education and highly skilled work is how society and policy permit new graduates to access wages and employment opportunities that match graduates' skills. However, there is a lot of variation in this regard across countries and in many countries, the graduates are doomed to be overqualified, underpaid, or even unemployed, which may cause political dissatisfaction among them. Ansell and Gingrich (2017) state that higher education systems vary dramatically in their reliance on private funds, their stratification and the ways they shape and reshape class and race relations in society.

In response to this policy ambition, there have been a number of efforts to estimate the supply and demand of, for example, tertiary graduates as well as project these estimates into the future (Biagi et al., 2020). However, these efforts may not always take into account the

possible dynamic (reinforcing and/or balancing) effects present in such systems. Therefore, it can be argued that developing a system dynamics model capturing the evolution of supply and demand for labour as well as their mismatch at different skill levels could be of interest to further enrich this ongoing debate.

3 Research questions

Accordingly, this paper aims to simulate the dynamics of skills development (education), skills supply (workforce size) and skills demand (number of jobs), with a focus on tertiary education as well as policy and social factors possibly moderating those dynamics. In particular, the intention is to explore the mechanisms driving over-education and what possible factors influence these mechanisms. More broadly, the main research question addressed in this paper is:

To what extent a meaningful system dynamics model could be constructed to represent, in line with actual data, the evolution of supply and demand for skills as well as their mismatch in the European Union over time?

4 Methodology

The objective of this study is to test the possibility, based on actual statistical data, to model the evolution and dynamics of the (mis)match between the available workforce and demand for it depending on the level of skills possessed by people and those required at work. This included identifying appropriate measures and data sources, building an SD model and adjusting the model so that simulated values correspond to real data.

4.1 Main definitions

Three broad skill levels (low; medium and high) have been defined in line with international statistical standards and regular practice (Eurostat, 2016). Notably, the level of skills of a person can be defined based on the highest educational attainment level, using the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED). Similarly, the level of skills demanded in a job can be defined based on the occupational group to which the particular job belongs, using the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO). A match is assumed where the level of education corresponds to the level of skills required in a job.

4.2 Key elements of the model

The central element of the model is the education system, which represents the flow of individuals through education until they exit (or drop out) from it. Subsequently, they enter the labour market, contributing to the pool of individuals with the same level of education, who are available for work. For reasons of simplicity, there are only two education levels represented in the system - upper secondary education and tertiary education at the bachelor's degree level.

However, these two education levels, in terms of absolute student numbers represent the two primary points of transition from education to the labour market. This is due to the fact that in a large number of countries individuals are legally obliged to attend school until the end of upper-secondary education, thus there are only very few persons leaving school earlier. Furthermore, for the purpose of this model, individuals who would complete education at higher levels beyond Bachelor's degree would remain counted as highly skilled and thus would not change the skills supply or mismatch dynamics as measured in the model.

Individuals, who complete education either at the upper secondary or tertiary level then enter the labour market contributing to the pool of individuals with the same level of education, who are available for work. At the end of their working life, individuals also retire and thus are

removed from these workforce pools. The model also represents the fact, that not all persons, who are available for work, are actually working. Also, in real life, the probability of employment differs depending on their level of education (skills). This is represented in the model by differentiating the proportion of individuals who are employed, in line with the actual data of employment rates of individuals with different levels of education.

Another important element of the model is the representation of skills demand. This is shown as the number of jobs assumed to require a certain level of education (and thus skills), with a focus on jobs at medium and high skill levels and their change over time. Ultimately, the model allows calculating skills supply-demand imbalance indicators, i.e., to what extent the number of employed individuals, at each skills level, is larger (or smaller) as compared to the number of jobs available at that skills level. Mismatch indicators are standardized, showing negative values when, at a certain skills level, there is an undersupply of the workforce, positive values when there is an oversupply and a zero when there is a perfect match between the two.

Finally, the model also includes two moderating factors (dynamic hypotheses). The first one is that the size of high skilled workforce will influence positively the relative attractiveness of higher education. This is justified by the so-called crowding-out phenomenon (Cockx & Dejemeppe, 2002) when highly educated persons replace less educated ones in jobs that normally do not require high levels of skills. This phenomenon can also be inferred from the relatively significant share of university graduates in the EU, who are considered over-educated for the jobs they do. For example, according to Eurostat experimental statistics, the share of overqualified university graduates in the EU in 2020 was estimated to be 21.5%, increasing slightly from the 20.4% observed in 2008.

The second moderating factor (dynamic hypothesis) is that the size of the highly skilled workforce may have an impact on the policy intended to limit the oversupply of certain skills (i.e., aiming to balance skills supply and demand). Existing literature argues that over-education may be negative effects both at the individual level (through relatively lower wages as compared to their well-matched pairs (De Santis et al., 2021) as well as at the macro level (waste of public resources invested in education (Caroleo & Pastore, 2015)). Therefore, it can be hypothesized that high levels of over-education would likely lead to policy efforts to reduce the number of individuals who acquire higher education degrees. Such policy reaction (among several others) is also suggested in the literature (McGuinness et al., 2018).

4.3 Data sources, model calibration and simulation

The model proposed in this study was simulated using Vensim PLE software. It was calibrated to perform in line with actual data, which is available for the majority of the indicators, except for the two dynamic hypotheses - the effect of the attractiveness of higher education and the policy response to skills oversupply, which are difficult to observe empirically.

The actual data was sourced from two data sources, both available online on the Eurostat data depository: the Unesco-OECD-Eurostat (UOE) joint data collection on education systems and the European Labour Force Survey (LFS). The model was calibrated to represent the evolution of the system as observed through actual data between 2011 and 2020 and then simulate the evolution of the system for 70 years into the future, e.g. until around 2080.

However, it must be noted that the realistic behaviour of the system is only expected to last up until around 2030-2040, as beyond these dates it is expected that a number of assumptions of the current model would not hold any more. This in particular concerns the currently relatively low rate of retirement of highly skilled workers, which would be expected to start increasing, when population cohorts with a higher share of highly skilled workers start reaching retirement age. In other words, currently, the outflow of highly-skilled workers from the available workforce is comparably low, as workers who graduated after the expansion of higher education in most countries still have not reached retirement age.

5 Results

Assuming that the key variables such as levels of educational enrolment and graduation, employment rates and job growth rates, will remain stable over time, it seems to be possible to simulate the behaviour of the system over time following the past trends.

5.1 Analysis of the trends in the past

Based on available data, we observe that during the last decade (or more specifically after 2013, which was the first year of the implementation of the new ISCED 2011 classification) student numbers in the secondary and tertiary education systems in the European Union on average have been remarkably stable. On the other hand, we do observe a continuous increase in the size of the workforce with a high level of education (and thus, presumably, a high level of skills) from 64.2 million in 2011 to almost 82 million in 2020. Similarly, we also observe a continuous, even if slower, increase in the number of jobs requiring a high level of skills - from nearly 70 million in 2011 up to almost 80 million in 2020. Absolute numbers reveal, that the size of high skilled workforce, over the period of nearly 10 years, increased by around 18 million, while the number of highly skilled jobs increased only by around 10 million. By 2020, the number of employed high-skilled individuals (at around 68 million) was still quite lower than the total number of high-skilled jobs (at nearly 80 million), a difference of around 13.3%.

5.2 Simulating the supply-demand imbalance of high-level skills

When looking over a 70-year horizon (assuming the starting year is 2011), the model estimates that the difference between employed high-skilled workforce and the number of high-skilled jobs would evolve from -24% in 2011 towards -12% in 2021, -0.04% in 2031 and +0.04% in 2041, moving from under to oversupply between the years 2035 and 2036 and finally stabilizing after the 2060s at around the rate of 0.113 (or 11.3% of oversupply).

Figure 1

Simulated evolution of high skills imbalance indicator between 2011 and 2081.

5.3 Simulating the supply-demand imbalance of medium-level skills

For medium skills imbalance, a shortage was also observed from 2011, which was declining for a couple of years before starting to increase again from around 2015-2017. The simulation

further extends this declining trend to proceed until the 2050s, then slowing down and around the 2060s presumably stabilizing at a rate of -0.2 (or around 20% of shortage).

Figure 2

Simulated evolution of medium skills imbalance indicator between 2011 and 2081.

5.4 Simulating the effects of change in immigration levels

One outstanding finding when calibrating the model was the identification of the inflow of highly-skilled workers beyond levels accounted for through the output of education systems in the EU. This inflow has been presumed to represent the net migration of high-skilled labour in the EU. Interesting system behaviour can be observed when modifying the rate of immigration of high-skilled workers, increasing from 1 million per year (as has been on average observed in the data) to 2 million per year. In this case, one can observe a much more rapid increase in the over-supply of high-skill labour, peaking around the year 2040 and later stabilizing at the level of around 0.175 (or 17.5% of oversupply).

Figure 3

Simulated evolution of high skills imbalance indicator between 2011 and 2081, with an elevated rate of immigration

5.5 Modelling changes in policy sensitivity

Another way to explore the functioning of the model is to assess the impact of the mediating factors (dynamic hypotheses). In the baseline model, the two mediating factors were set not to have an effect until the high skills oversupply ratio goes above 0. When oversupply becomes above zero, they are then modelled to affect the probability of enrollment in higher education, in proportion to the size of the oversupply, multiplied by a factor of 5. Each of the moderating factors acts in an opposite direction, i.e., the crowding-out effect increases the attractiveness of higher education and thus affects the probability of enrollment positively, while the skills oversupply reduction policy affects the probability of enrollment in higher education negatively. These crowding-out or policy sensitivity factors could be adjusted.

For example, when reducing the policy sensitivity factor to 1, there is a strong increase in the number of tertiary education students and the high skills oversupply indicator grows without any stabilization and reaching by 2080 the value of 0.5 (or 50% of oversupply). Conversely, increasing the policy sensitivity factor to 10 makes policy react very strongly to the appearance of high skills oversupply, which promptly leads to a reduction in the number of tertiary education students from an initial 2.6 to 1.68 million and to a stabilization of the high skills oversupply index at a much lower value of 0.048 (or 4.8% of oversupply).

5.6 Observations from model calibration

The model parameters were calibrated so that the behaviour of all indicators in the model for which real data is available would approximate, as best as possible, real data. Indicators, for which direct observations were not available are the drop-out rates and retirement rates. Thus, the real drop-out rate was estimated as the difference between the number of new students and the number of graduates, given that within education systems the total number of students enrolled remained stable. Furthermore, it was observed that at the upper-secondary education level, the number of new entrants largely correspond to the number of graduates, eliminating the need for a drop-out variable at that education level. This, however, is counter-intuitive, as other data sources suggest a notable number of drop-outs from secondary education. For example, based on the results from the 2016 EU LFS ad-hoc module, it was estimated that in 2016 there may have been around 800.000 young people aged 18-24, who report having started and then leaving upper secondary education¹. This may be a measurement artefact and it deserves further analysis.

Another caveat was identified when modelling the evolution of the total size of the workforce depending on skill levels. Such modelling requires setting the volumes of both inflows of new members into those groups (i.e., those who complete education) as well as those who leave those groups (i.e. retire and leave the labour market). Direct data on annual retirement rates are difficult to access, thus a simplified calculation was done to estimate this rate based on the size of cohorts aged 60-64 (which is available from the EU LFS) and dividing it by five to get the size of cohort leaving the workforce every year. Such estimation revealed an accelerating rate of retirement of individuals with medium-level skills, but this acceleration appeared only after 2016. This may also be some data-source-specific artefact and may need further exploration.

Similar estimations made for the highly skilled workforce, however, revealed that there seems to be a significant gap between the inflow (new graduates), estimated outflow (retirement) and the changes in the stock of this workforce group. Notably, the simulated retirement rate seemed to be too big to allow the growth of the highly skilled workforce, observed from the data. Actually, to make sure that the highly skilled workforce would increase

¹ https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfso_16elvncom&lang=en

at the observed rate, the retirement rate should be zero or even slightly negative - which is highly unlikely. Thus, an additional factor of "immigration" was added, to account for this unexplained inflow of highly skilled workers.

Overall, for the calibration of the model, it was aimed to use, where possible, stable volumes of inflows and outflows, only using accelerating or decelerating rates where a significant deviation from real data was observed, such as the acceleration of retirement rate of medium-skilled individuals after 2016. The final data set including both actual and calibrated values is presented in the technical appendix, in Table A1.

6 Discussion and conclusions

Overall, the model seems to suggest that an absolute oversupply of high skills could be reached around the year 2035 if the parameters as set out in the model remain similar to the real-life conditions during this period. The model also suggests that if the effect of two opposite moderating factors with equal strength is included, it could be expected that the skills oversupply ratio could stabilize at around the year 2045. In this model, such moderating factors include a "reinforcing" feedback loop between high skills oversupply and higher education attractiveness, based on the notion of "crowding out" and a "balancing" loop of policy, aiming to limit the waste of public resources resulting in over-education.

The overall process of modelling the supply, demand and mismatch of skills proved to be a relatively straightforward (even if much simplified) exercise. Conversely, setting out the behaviour of moderating factors – the attractiveness of tertiary education and policy of managing skills oversupply - was more challenging to model. This is due to the fact that no data were identified to directly represent the behaviour of such factors in the real world. Some other notable findings from our analysis include the observation, that the reported number of university graduates is too small to fully explain the increase in the size of high skilled workforce in the EU during the last ten years as well as the sensitivity of the model to rates of retirement at different skills levels, which seem to be less stable than expected.

When interpreting the results of this modelling exercise, a number of caveats need to be taken into consideration. For example, the size of the high-skilled workforce is possibly underestimated. Notably, earlier work (Sekmoka, 2021; Sekmoka et al., 2020) has indicated, that some of the medium-level vocational qualifications, particularly those at ISCED levels 4 and 5) are likely to be a good fit for some of the high-skilled jobs particularly those at ISCO level 3). Such adjustment, as calculated for the reference year 2016, resulted at that time in an estimated EU-level high-skilled workforce shortage of only several percentage points (Sekmoka et al., 2020), as opposed to almost 20% shortage as estimated in the model presented in this paper. Other uncertainties, as already mentioned before, include past and future migration rates, retirement rates or drop-out rates from different education levels and all these suggest that care is needed when drawing real-life conclusions from this rather experimental exercise.

Finally, the role of education should not be judged exclusively from the labour market matching perspective, as there may be a variety of effects of mismatch, some of them positive while others negative. Thus, it can be assumed that in some cases the presence of a mismatch may be preferable from an economic or social perspective. At the same time, decisions on the optimal and preferable levels of education should be well-considered. Hopefully, this exercise illustrates the potential of labour market modelling to enrich the evidence base used to inform such decisions.

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Biographical notes

Mantas Sekmokas is currently an independent consultant. Until mid-2020, he was working for nearly a decade for the European Commission, providing evidence-based advice to underpin EU skills, VET and AL policy initiatives. His academic background includes a MSc in Information Studies from the University of Amsterdam (UvA), a MSc in Cognitive and Decision Sciences from the University College London (UCL) as well as a MSc and a BA in management.

Dr. **Sai** is a Lecturer/Assistant professor at Maastricht University and The Open University of The Netherlands. He has a Ph.D. in Computer Science from SFI Centre for Software Ireland where his research focused on better understanding what decentralization entails in a distributed systems context. His research has been featured in several national and international media outlets (Forbes, Economic Times). His work on centralization has been foundational to policy development around cryptocurrencies. Dr. Sai's work has been cited by SEC in the US, OECD, Ada Lovelace Institute, and Norges Bank in their policy documents. He has also worked as visiting scholar at the University of California, Berkeley where he continued working on promoting scientific rigor in decentralized research. In the past, he has worked as a lecturer at Trinity College Dublin and the University of Amsterdam.

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Naomi Tilon has been working for a number of years for the Dutch banking industry in roles related to data analysis. She is also currently a student at the University of Amsterdam within the Information Studies domain.

- A reinforcing loop of the crowding-out effects leads to an increase in the attractiveness of higher education. As discussed before, the literature points out that there may be crowding-out effects when there is a significant presence of over-skilled individuals in the labour market. Notably, when competing for less-skilled jobs, over-skilled individuals often out-compete individuals with lower levels of education, even if that is the level most appropriate for particular jobs. As a consequence, in case of oversupply of highly-skilled labour, less skilled labour may appear in an ever more precarious situation - being able to access only the least attractive, lowest paying jobs or not being able to find employment at all. Such a situation would make the relative benefits of higher education persistently larger and thus would be an incentive for more people to pursue higher education. This would even be the case in a situation where the number of high-skilled jobs would be limited, as de-facto high skills level would become a prerequisite to access any type of employment.

In order to run simulations, a Stock and Flow diagram (SFD) was built (see Figure A2 below). Diagrams are ways of representing the structure of a system with more detailed information than is shown in a causal loop diagram. Stocks are levels, they are fundamental to generating behavior in a system; flows can be considered as rates, which cause stocks to change by increasing or decreasing them.

Figure A2
Stock and flow diagram

2 Key assumptions

From a very general perspective, the key assumption behind the model is that skills supply (e.g., through education) and skills demand (e.g. through job creation) are independent processes and the main mechanisms linking those systems are the individuals' (households') and policy reactions to the imbalance between the two, subsequently effecting skills supply (education) systems. Thus, three high-level elements are the skills supply system; the skills demand system and the feedback loops connecting them. In addition, a significant number of other assumptions, to simplify the model, have been made (though compiling an exhaustive list of all the assumptions behind the model is probably not feasible):

- Exclusion of many other possible links within the system, for example, the impact policy has on such variables as immigration, employment rates and job growth rates;
- Exclusion of the possible interaction between feedback loops - for example, the impact of popular opinion on the attractiveness of higher education on oversupply mitigation policy;
- Exclusion for temporal effects, i.e., future expectations. Different actors may have different expectation horizons and may start reacting much more in advance to expected changes in conditions as opposed to other actors;
- Exclusion of the majority of demographic effects on population variables (different cohort sizes; population ageing; falling birth rates);
- Using constant rates of changes, for example as regards retirement or as regards the growth in jobs, which are unlikely to persist in the long term.

3 Key uncertainties

It is also important to note the two major sources of uncertainty in the model, which may limit its validity, especially over the long term:

- The largest scope of uncertainty is related to the functioning and the mechanisms of feedback loops. As mentioned in the text before, it is difficult to directly observe the effects of moderating factors such as policy reaction or attractiveness of higher education, their change over time and their relation to other factors. Thus, at this stage, these feedback loops are mostly for illustration purposes and they would deserve much more detailed analysis before their effects could be established with more reliability;
- Another significant scope of uncertainty is the long-term changes in the structure of the job market (i.e., long-term evolution of structural change). Until recently, structural change has been progressing across most countries in a rather linear manner, with job jobs moving first from agriculture to industry and later from industry to services. But these mechanisms lately seem not to hold any more, as many developing countries are not able to build a strong industrial base. There are also fears that automation may start negatively affecting service jobs. Thus, overall, long-term projections of skills demand have a large element of uncertainty.

4 Ordinary differential equations

The overall model consists of six stocks; thus six ordinary differential equations (ODEs) can be developed: the stock of secondary school students, the stock of university students, the stock of medium-skilled workforce, the stock of highly skilled workforce, the stock of medium-skilled jobs and the stock of high skilled jobs. Most of the equations are rather straightforward as they do not have many interaction terms with other parameters in the model.

The ODE for the stock of secondary school students includes a fixed inflow of new students and an outflow of graduates, who may either choose a higher education pathway or enter the labour market, with x_1 being the stock of secondary school students at the time t ; a , b and c are model parameters; the model includes two inter-dependent outflows from the stock which always have to sum-up to 100%. It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dx_1}{Dt} = a - \frac{x_1}{b} - \left(\frac{x_1}{c} - \frac{x_1}{b} \right) = a - \frac{x_1}{c}$$

The ODE for the stock of university students includes an inflow of secondary school graduates who enter university and two outflows – graduated students and drop-outs, with x_1 being the stock of secondary school students at time t ; x_2 being the stock of university students at time t ; b , d and e being model parameters; the model includes two independent outflows from the stock. It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dx_2}{Dt} = \frac{x_1}{b} - \frac{x_2}{d} - \frac{x_2}{e}$$

The ODE for the stock of medium-skilled workforce includes an inflow of secondary school students who enter labour market and an inflow of drop-outs from higher education minus a fixed “retirement” outflow, with y_1 being the stock of medium-skilled labour at time t ; x_1 being the stock of secondary school students at time t ; x_2 being the stock of university students at time t ; c , b , e and f being model parameters; furthermore, even if outflow in the model is set as a fixed parameter, in a more precise model it could be expressed as an interaction term between the stock (y_1) and one or several parameters. It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dy_1}{Dt} = \left(\frac{x_1}{c} - \frac{x_1}{b} \right) + \frac{x_2}{e} - f$$

The ODE for the stock of high skilled workforce includes an inflow of university graduates, plus a fixed inflow of immigration, minus a fixed “retirement” outflow, with y_2 being the stock of high skilled labour at time t , x_2 being the stock of university students at time t , d , g and h being model parameters; furthermore, even if outflow in the model is set as a fixed parameter, in a more precise model it could be expressed as an interaction term between the stock (y_1) and one or several parameters. It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dy_2}{Dt} = \frac{x_2}{d} + g - h$$

The ODE for the stock of medium-skilled jobs includes the inflow of a net rate of change set as a fixed parameter i , with z_1 being the stock of medium-skilled jobs at time t . It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dz_1}{Dt} = i$$

The ODE for the stock of high-skilled jobs includes the inflow of a net rate of change set as a fixed parameter j , with z_2 being the stock of medium-skilled jobs at time t . It can thus be expressed as:

$$\frac{Dz_2}{Dt} = j$$

5 Stocks, parameters and constants

The stocks and flows used in the model are as follows:

- The stock of upper-secondary school students. The stock is a function of an inflow of new entrants into upper-secondary education and an outflow of graduates from upper-secondary education, with a portion of graduates entering the labour market directly and another portion entering further studies in higher education. The initial value is set at 17.5 million, in line with the actual data varying between 17 million and 18 million. Data sources: Eurostat, UOE data collection, online table code for the stock of students is [educ_uae_enrs05], online table code for the new entrants is [educ_uae_ent01] and the online table code for the graduates is [educ_uae_grad01].
- The stock of university students at the Bachelor's level. The stock is a function of an inflow of new entrants into higher education Bachelor's programmes and an outflow of graduates and drop-outs. The initial value is set at 10 million, in line with the actual data fluctuating between 9.8 and 10.7 million students. Data sources: Eurostat, UOE data collection, online table code for the stock of students is [educ_uae_enra02], for the new entrants is [educ_uae_ent01] and for graduates is [educ_uae_grad01].
- The stock of medium-skilled workforce. The stock is a function of an inflow of graduates from secondary education who enter the labour market as well as drop-outs from tertiary education as well as a "retirement" outflow. As retirement levels are not observed directly, they are estimated as one-fifth of the size of the medium-skilled cohort at ages 60-64. The outflow is also affected by a sudden increase in its rate observed from the year 2016. The initial value of the stock is set at 130 million, in line with the actual data varying between 131 and 130 million. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_pgaed].
- The stock of high skilled workforce. The stock is a function of an inflow of graduates from tertiary education; an inflow of immigrants and a "retirement" outflow. As retirement levels are not observed directly, they are estimated as one-fifth of the size of high skilled cohort at ages 60-64. The initial value of the stock is set at 64.2 million, in line with actual data. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_pgaed].
- The stock of medium-skilled jobs. The stock is a function of the net rate of change, calibrated based on actual data. The initial value of the stock is set at 92.6 million, in line with actual data. The net rate of change is fixed at -0.25 million/year, which is an average of the actual data which varies between -3.1 to +1.0 million/year. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_egais].
- The stock of high-skilled jobs. The stock is a function of the net rate of change, calibrated based on actual data. The initial value of the stock is set at 69.7 million, in line with actual data. The net rate of change is fixed at +1 million, which is an average of the actual data which varies between -0.1 to +1.9 million/year. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_egais].

The other key parameters in the model include:

- The employment rate of the medium-skilled workforce. It is set as a fixed value of 0.7 (or 70%), calibrated based on actual data which fluctuates between 68.7% and 73.4%. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_ergaed].
- The size of the employed medium-skilled workforce is a multiplication of the total medium-skilled workforce and medium-skilled employment rate.
- The employment rate of the highly skilled workforce. It is set as a fixed value of 0.83 (or 83%), calibrated based on actual data which fluctuates between 81.3% and 84.8%. Data source: Eurostat, EU labour force survey, online table code [lfsa_ergaed].
- The size of the employed high-skilled workforce is a multiplication of the total high-skilled workforce and high-skilled employment rate.
- Policy intensity factor. It is set subjectively as a fixed factor with a value of 5, in order to make the effects of the policy reaction visible over the simulation time horizon.
- The skills oversupply reduction policy is set as a conditional equation with a value of 1 if the oversupply index is below or equal to 0. When the oversupply index is above zero, its value is calculated as 1 minus (-) the value of oversupply, multiplied by the policy intensity factor.
- Crowding out intensity factor. It is set subjectively as a fixed factor with a value of 5, in order to make the effects of the crowding-out visible over the simulation time horizon.
- The crowding out function is set as a conditional equation with a value of 1 if the oversupply index is below or equals to 0. Then oversupply index is above zero, its value is calculated as 1 plus(+) the value of oversupply, multiplied by the crowding-out intensity factor.
- The attractiveness of higher education equals to the crowding out function value.

6 Parameter tuning

In calibrating the model, it was aimed to reach model behaviour during the years for which data is available as close as possible to the real data for both actual and modelled data. However, several of the indicators for simplicity reasons were set as rounded figures (though still approximating well the actual data). These include the stock of medium-skilled workforce, net rates of change of jobs, retirement outflows, immigration, etc. Besides these adjustments, only very limited further fine-tuning were required to further adjust the performance of the model, which includes adding 0.1 value to the drop-out from higher education, adding 0.1 to as well as subtracting 0.002 from the inflow of students into higher education. The calibration between actual data and model parameters is presented in Figure A3 below.

Table A1
Calibration between actual data and the model parameters (all figures are in millions)

Domain	Variable	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
School	Entry - actual	-	-	4.3	4.8	4.6	4.6	4.7	4.6	4.7	-
	Entry - model	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6
	Students - actual	-	-	18.0	17.8	17.0	16.8	17.6	17.7	17.6	-
	Students - model	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5	17.5
	Total graduates - actual	-	-	-	4.8	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.5	4.6	-
	Total graduates - model	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6	4.6
	Graduates to uni - model	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	-
	Graduates to work - model	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
University	Entry - actual	-	-	-	-	-	2.6	2.6	2.7	2.8	-
	Entry - model	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6
	Students - actual	-	-	10.5	10.5	9.9	9.8	10.5	10.5	10.7	-
	Students - model	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
	Graduates - actual	-	-	2.0	2.0	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.1	-
	Graduates - model	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Dropout - actual estimate	-	-	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	-
	Dropout - model	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
High skilled workforce	Stock - actual	64.2	66.4	68.5	70.4	72.1	73.5	75.2	77.1	79.2	81.9
	Stock - model	64.2	66.2	68.2	70.2	72.2	74.2	76.2	78.2	80.2	82.2
	Immigration - estimate actual	-	-	-	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.9
	Immigration - model	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Retirement - estimate actual	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.3
	Retirement - model	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Medium skilled workforce	Stock - actual	131.3	130.9	130.8	131.2	130.6	130.1	129.1	127.9	126.9	125.4
	Stock - model	130.0	130.0	130.0	130.0	130.0	130.1	129.1	128.1	127.1	126.1
	Retirement - estimate actual	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.4	2.5	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.7	2.8
	Retirement - model	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	2.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6
High skilled jobs	Stock - actual	69.7	70.2	70.6	71.7	73.1	74.8	76.2	77.8	79.6	79.6
	Stock - model	69.7	70.7	71.7	72.7	73.7	74.7	75.7	76.7	77.7	78.7
	Net change - actual	-	0.5	0.4	1.1	1.4	1.7	1.4	1.6	1.9	-0.1
	Net change - model	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Medium skilled jobs	Stock - actual	92.6	91.9	90.7	91.2	91.6	92.3	93.2	93.6	93.5	90.4
	Stock - model	92.6	92.4	92.1	91.9	91.6	91.4	91.1	90.9	90.6	90.4
	Net change - actual	-	-0.7	-1.2	0.5	0.3	0.7	1.0	0.4	-0.1	-3.1
	Net change - model	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3